

A REVIEW : THE ROLE OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract :

Nanotechnology is an emerging field, comprising the development of materials with 5-200 nanometers in size. Like many other fields advances in nanotechnology is utilized in medicine also specially for therapeutic drug delivery and treatment for a variety of diseases and disorders. The drug is dissolved and entrapped into biodegradable nanoparticles which are specially designed to absorb drug and protecting it against chemical and enzymatic degradation. Nanotechnology is helping the delivery of pharmacologically active molecules for sitespecific action with accurate dose. The most promising aspect of utilizing nanotechnology in drug delivery system is lowering of side effects by depositing the active agent in the morbid region only with accurate dose. Nanoparticles for drug delivery are prepared by a variety of materials such as proteins, polysaccharides and synthetic polymers. The selection of material depends on many factors such as the size of nanoparticles, inherent properties of the drug, surface characteristics such as charge and permeability, degree of

biodegradability and most important the route of drug delivery. Gold nanoparticles are widely utilized for cancer therapy. Solid lipid nanoparticles have showed appreciable results in anti-cancer and antiviral therapy. Nanofibers, Nanosuspensions etc. are also in use. The use of nanotechnology has facilitated the delivery of many drugs in an appropriate amount and in a targeted manner.

Keywords:

Drug delivery, Liposomes, Gold nanoparticles, Drug targeting, Biodegradability, dendrimers. Solid lipid nanoparticles, SPIO nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes, silica nanoparticles, magnetic nanoparticles, Liposomes.

Introduction

Nanoscience is the only platform to discover the new properties of matter by collaborating with conventional fields such as applied health, molecular chemistry, molecular science, pharmaceutical science, optics, and even engineering. In the recent few decades, the combination of science and technology are often well architected to defence the challenges in the field of medicinal and health sciences by providing a more effective health system, nano-medicinal tools, and therapeutic approaches. Historically, the term nanotechnology was first

time coined in 1974 by Professor N. Taniguchi. Soon after, Drexler developed and published the first concept (Feynman's ideas) of nanotechnology in the book entitled “Vehicles of creation: the arrival of the nanotechnology era” in 1986 . Currently, the impact of nanotechnology on human and animal can be arising new avenue for investigation and transformation of health science and becomes the imperative subject for consideration as a therapeutic tool. Nanotechnology is a very shady multidisciplinary area invented to engineering biological matters such as atoms, molecules, and supramolecules at nanoscale range approx 1–100 nm to hold promise against existing challenges by creating new devices and characterisation of material structure technologies with unique properties to study and understand the lethal biological problems followed by diagnosis and cure of disease . Nanotechnology has highlighted as the most dominating and commercially invented technology of these decades, considerably being very crucial for human lives. Of note, living cells component are extremely crucial machinery with very tiny size (nanoscale). They are robustly involved in almost all biological activity, including cell signalling, metabolism, energy production, and nutrient transport. Therefore, it can be deemed that nanotechnology as an essential candidate that can offer new technologies at the individual matter level to deal with biology and medicine for therapeutic purposes . Various nanoscale materials are invented with several clinical advantages; nano-medicine is emerging as

a gold standard in health sciences . The pathophysiological and clinically correlated modulation of diseased/abnormal tissues/cells offers numerous advantages for producing and delivering several nanomedicine products. Thus, tissue-specific drug targeting approaches may have a choice of strategy to overcome disease prognosis . In the recent few years, nanomaterials, preferentially metal nanoparticles, have received more attention in the diverse area of medical science. Optimising the synthesis of nanomaterials such as polymers, micelles, dendrimers, liposomes, emulsions, nanocapsules, and nanoparticles has now become a prolific area of study.

In the current scenario, nanomedicine is one of the leading applications of nanotechnology, which committed to developing nanoscale medicinal tools to provide an effective health care system. This approach allows us to understand human physiology in a better way to fight against several deadly diseases such as cancer and cardiovascular diseases. The significance of nanomedicine is mainly applied for imaging, diagnosis of diseases, tissue engineering, and architecting more efficient, cost-effective and safe drug delivery systems to precisely delivering drugs to target sites which can accelerate treatment outcome via reducing off-target effect and toxicities . According to Bebo et al., to date, approximately 51 nanomedicines have been approved by US-FDA, followed by 77 products are in the pre-clinical stage, of which approx 40% are in the clinical trial phase. Most of these approved nanomaterials are polymeric liposomal and nanocrystal formulations.

However, the scientist thinks to develop more efficient material including micelles, protein-based nanoparticles (NPs) as well as a variety of inorganic and metallic particles in clinical trials .

Nanotechnology can hold promise to promote revolutionary advances in medicine, communications, genomics, and robotics in human health, which can result in immense clinical benefits. It is very vast and diverse to discuss and explore the whole nanotechnology application. Still, in contrast to this, the most significant advantage of nanotechnology tools and products may have great values in human health in global contexts The history of Evolution Timeline of Nanotechnology in Medical science has been shown in Table .

This Review highlights the significance of nanotechnology in human health with particular emphasis on its nano-medicinal application in imaging, screening, diagnosis, targeted drug delivery systems, and effective treatment strategies for human diseases. Here, we also depicted the risk associated with this and its future advancement in medicinal sciences.

Classification of nanotechnology (nanomaterial's/nanoparticles)

Nanoparticles are classified according to their dimensionality, morphology, state, and chemical composition [11]. Nanoparticles are a class of material under nanotechnology containing substances in the form of particle size around 10–100 nm. These materials are broadly divided into various dimensions such as 0D, 1D [12]. According to some finding, these materials, size can influence the physiochemical visualisation (optical properties) of substances like gold (Au), platinum (Pt), silver (Ag),

Types of Nanoparticles:

A range of nanoparticles are available for using them as a drug delivery tool. Mainly four types of nanoparticles are discussed below.

- Metallic nanoparticles like silver Gold ,Cadmium,Sereniumetc**
- Lipid nanoparticles like Liposome**
- Polymeric nanoparticles like Dendrimer, poly micelles**
- Biological nanoparticles-BSA(Bovine serum Albumin)**

Polymeric nanoparticles:

They are solid particles with size range of 10- 100nm .They can be prepared from biodegradable and non-biodegradable

polymers or materials (Arias JL et.al., 2006). Due to their small size. They can be easily taken up by the cells and increases the accumulation of drugs at target site (Singh et.al., 2006) .A wide spectrum of hydrophobic and hydrophilic drugs can be loaded in these nanoparticles. The surrounding of these polymeric materials consist of functional groups that can be modified with the help of targeting ligands (Ahmed et.al.,2006and Pandey et.al.,2006) Different methods for immobilization of drug in nanoparticles can be used. The polymer PCL (Poly (Ecaprolectone) and PLGA (PolyLactone-coglycoside) are compared, They are efficiently taken up by immune cells due to their hydrophobicity. (Singh J et.al.,2006) .These nanoparticles are also explored for asthma(Seong et.al.,2006).tuberculosis (Pandey et.al.,2006) and hypertension (Kimura et.al.,2009) besides cancer.(Azarmi et.al.,2006). some other applications of polymeric nanoparticles also include oral delivery of insulin(Damage C.et al.,2007) ,targeted drug delivery for Alzheimer 's disease (Hartig W. et.al.,.2003)In order to target the drug at specific site,the drug is conjugated to a cell specific ligand that can reach the organs. Drugs are incorporated into nanoparticles by dissolution, adsorption or entrapment so that nanoparticles can provide efficient release of drug at targeted site. Literature review on polymeric nanoparticles proves that these are quite efficient and suitable for using them in drug delivery.

Liposomes:

The word liposome originated from two Greek words namely lipo and soma which means fat and body that's why it is named so it is composed of phospholipids mainly. Liposomes were the first compounds investigated as drug carriers. They are colloidal carriers, usually with size range of 80–300 nm. Liposomes are mainly composed of phospholipid like phosphatidylglycerol, Phosphatidic choline as discussed by Moussaoui et.al., 2002 and Banerjee R. in 2001. The characteristics and features of liposomes mainly rely on the choice of lipid, size, constitution and method by which its preparation is done.. Lipids are considered to be suitable chemicals to formulate solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and nanocapsules. Liposomes have been reported to show a strong potential for effective drug delivery to the site of action by increasing the solubility of drugs and improving their pharmacokinetic properties, such as the therapeutic index of chemotherapeutic agents, rapid metabolism and a significant reduction of harmful side effects. Modified liposomes are an interesting type of such lipid structures. Drugs which act selectively on a particular tissue can be designed by the use of multifunctional liposomes, containing the specific proteins, antigens, or other biological substances. In the past few years, many drugs with liposomal delivery systems have been approved and some are in clinical trials. In the market, a range of liposomal drugs are available for many diseases. Anticancer liposomal drugs are also being studied by many scientists and commercialized till date; a few examples of them are mentioned below. One another property of liposomes make them unique

from others is that drugs with different lipophilicity can be encapsulated in liposomes which are stated below : • 1-phospholipid layer, • 2-in the entrapped substance • 3-volume or mass at the bilayer surface

Mechanism:

A Liposome has a hydrophobic membrane i.e. they do not have ability to form hydrogen bonds with water (Water hating) as well as a core in them. These hydrophobic membranes are linked with lipid bilayer. So liposome can be used either with hydrophobic or with hydrophilic molecules .the contents of a liposome can be easily delivered to the particular site i.e. diseased tissue in the body by linking the lipid bilayer with the cell membrane in which the delivery is to be done. The whole mechanism is very quick and easy as discussed by Cevc, G; Richardsen, H in 1993. They can be delivered by mixing or preparing in solution of DNA.] (Barenholz Y G, 000).Liposomes pH is constructed according to the drug with which it has to be used or with a substance it has to be coated or linked .At neutralization, The drug's as well as the liposome's inside pH will be neutralized, which makes its movement easier and quick through the membrane i.e. without any hindrance of pH or interference by other membranes. The mechanism with which drugs can be delivered with the help of liposomes is diffusion that is movement of a substance or a compound down a concentration gradient. Very different techniques can be used

to deliver the drugs with empty liposomes having a transmembrane pH gradient and in such methods in order to reduce toxic effects the vesicles of liposomes acts as the scavengers. (Bertrand et.al., 2010) Liposomes are used as drug carrier due to their ability of preventing degradation of drugs and reduce side effects. Liposome has many disadvantages include low encapsulation efficiency, Leakage of drug, poor stability. To overcome all these limitations surface polymers like polyethylene glycol can be used to improve liposome's stability. Other vesicular structures like ethosomes,niosomes can be used for transdermal delivery .Liposomes has many applications like drug delivery to enhance skin permeation of drugs ,drug delivery to lungs by nabulisation and also in treatment of parasitic infections.

List of clinically approved liposomal drugs :

- **Liposomal amphotericin B**
- **Liposomal doxorubicin**
- **Liposomal IRIV vaccine**
- **Liposomal verteporfin**

Manufacturing :

There are different factors on which preparation methods of lipids depends are as discussed by Gomezghens et.al., in 2006 and Mozafari et.al., in 2008 mentioned below

- The physical and chemical characteristics of the material which is to be encapsulated into the medium**
- The actual concentration of the entrapped material**
- The size range , dispersion level as well as shelflife of the vesicles**
- The possibility of large-scale production of safe ,improved and effective liposomal products** **Methods of Fabrication for liposomes**
- In this way, many other nanoparticles are produced like dendrimers are produced by solvent, microemulsions and solvent diffusion.**
- Method of preparing polymeric micelles includes dialysis, solution casting, direct dissolution.**

Applications of liposomes as a drug delivery tool:

- Liposome is very important as we know many hydrophobic drugs like cyclosporin and paclitaxel are dissolved in surfactants and cosolvents for their administration inside the body of humans and these surfactants and solvents are toxic in particular doses of drug. In comparison to that liposomes are made from lipids which are non-toxic, user friendly and compatible as well as biodegradable which provide more effective and safe drug delivery.

- Liposomal drug delivery is more systematic, controlled as well as cost effective than hydrophobic and any other conventional drugs.

Nanocrystals: Nanocrystals are aggregates of molecules that can be combined into a crystal form. They have wide applications in chemical and biological engineering (W.C.Chan et.al., 2016 and Dabbousi et.al., 1997), but less in nanomedicine for drug

- **Nanotech and cancer: -**

Many nanoscientists used ethylene glycol mol. 1.0 to deliver therapeutic drug to cancer cells. Ethylene glycol stops WBCs from recognizing NPs as foreign material and allows them to circulate in the blood stream and attach to cancer cells. Researchers at IBM demonstrated drug delivery by hydrogels. So research

is going on to enhance the ability of drug carrying nanoparticles to enter tumors.

- **Anti-inflammatory:-**

Indomethacin is used as an agent. Nanoparticles have great role as on antiinflammatory agent.

- **Regenerative Medicine: -**

Its main aim is to strengthen the self-healing process of human body. Three main approaches of Regenerative Medicine includes

- 1. Cell band**

- 2. Biomaterials based**

- 3. Combined tissue engineering strategies. Stem cells have ability of self-renewal.**

- **Bioactive materials are used for hard tissue regeneration**

- **Bone regeneration: - bone tissue is made from collagenous fibers and calcium phosphate in the form of hydroxyl apatite with embedded osteoclasts. So, nanoscaffolds are provided for bone tissue generations. Nano scaffolds promote biomineralitala**

- **Carbon nanotubes which are discussed earlier are also used for selective differentiation into osteoblast like cells**

- **Nanotech in heart disease: - protein nanoparticles are applied to damaged portion of artery .Super Iron Oxide (SPIO) particles are also used for this propose**

- **It treats the defective heart valve.**
- **Detect and treat arterial plague if heart valves have wrong level of collagen, it will make valve floppy and stiff. so gold nanoparticles with collagen changes the properties of valves and repair the defective heart valve without surgery (University of South Caroline)**
- **Nanotech -in Ageing:- Nanoparticles are also of great choice as an anti-ageing agent. Drug molecules are attached with nanodiamond embedded in contact lenses and are in contact with tears, Provide more consistent dosing than eye drops.**
- **Nanotubes:-Capsules are used for releasing insulin when glucose level rise in order to control blood sugar level .**
- **Nanoparticles also have role in tacking autoimmune diseases by delivery autism for particular disease in blood stream.**

► Cancer treatment

Cancer is the leading cause of deaths worldwide. Cancer is believed to be a multi-stage carcinogenesis process involving various physiological cell functions, such as cell signalling and apoptosis, making it the most mysterious and complex disease. Numerous developments have been made in traditional cancer treatment, such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy, which appear to be far from successful. As it is hindered by some disadvantages such as chemoresistance and severe side

► Surgical blades

Surgical blades are being used since the awareness of several diseases from the ancient time itself. However, the advancement of surgical equipment is gaining attention due to the modification of the conventional surgical tool. For the progress of the surgical blades, these blades are being coated with a hard metal diamond and gold and other metal and being used. Furthermore, due to metal-coated diamond nanolayer, its properties change to low physical adhesion concerning its tissue, material,

► **The risk associated with nanotechnology**

Nanotechnology is an emerging field of research with a broad spectrum of applications, including human welfare, health care, medicine, etc. Together with these applications, concerns regarding the hazardous effect of these nanoparticles also drew the attention of many researchers and several works were done to analyse the toxicity of these nanoparticles. The conclusion of these researches suggests that nanoparticles' following properties can lead to toxic effects of these particles.

► **Lungs damage**

Inhalation of nanoparticles in any form leads to the passage of these nanoparticles to various organs such as the lungs, brain, liver, spleen, accumulation to the mucosal layers of the epidermis and this invasion results in toxic effects on physiology, for example-TiO₂ nanoparticles when exposed to rat model system inferred that the nanoforms of these compound are comparatively more toxic than the bulk material and lead to pulmonary inflammations.

► Skin damage

Pores present on the skin are another

► Limitation of nanomedicine

Nanomedicine is an entirely new genre and very little evidence exists on this genre. We still want to see the useful application of nanomedicine to be on the safe side; we should say it is always at the experimental phase. Due to less information about the disadvantages of nanomedicine, we can not confidently say what the health risks of nanotechnology are. Still, we can conform to the fact that nanoparticles can enter our bodies in many ways, which may give rise to much concern.

► Future perspective

The global nanomedicine market size is estimated at \$53 billion in 2009 and is projected to increase by 13.5% at the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) to more than \$100 billion in 2014. The vision of creating a more efficient system for the development of nano-products is limited. Understanding the biodistribution of nanomaterials within the body is a crucial step. This is linked to a second constraint, which requires imaging methods to investigate nanomedicine's biodistribution over time.

► CONCLUSION

So from above stated findings and advancements in the field of nanotechnology for drug delivery, it can be proved that nanoparticles are the best suitable carriers or vectors for drug delivery system in our body. As well as they provide the many advantages over the properties of conventional drug delivery methods. These nanocarriers are not only used as vectors for carrying the particular drug at specific site in the body ,they also acts as an coating over the drug in order to prevent their degradation that might be caused by the conditions inside the body. The nanoparticles has propounded the proper, sustainable and controlled release of drug inside the body. In comparison with the traditional and conventional methods they are more effective, less toxic as well as are cost effective. These are less toxic in the sense that adverse side effects can be

minimized by targeting the drug only at particular site of diseased tissue. These nanoparticles can be operated at molecular and cellular level. As the name suggests nanoparticles, they are having a size of nanometer; due to this feature they can easily cross the blood-brain-barrier (BBB). All these properties of nanoparticles make them effective at even their low doses. With all these positive characteristics of nanoparticles there are some limitations also which are now a days are the biggest challenge in front of nanomedicine that are their larger surface area and their small size due to which aggregates of these particles are formed which are very difficult to handle during the delivery of drug. Second limitation is the commercialization of these nanocarriers coated drugs, as we know many scientists are working on the production of new and effective nanoparticles for drug delivery but still there are only few nanoparticles which are commercially available in the market. The examples of which are mentioned the main course of this topic. Nanocarrier-drug conjugates can be sometimes easily phagocytosed by cells which can may toxic effects in non-diseased tissues or cells. The many other limitations of nanoparticles are also there like their poor drug loading ability as well as efficiency. The verification and validation of Quality of nanoinstruments and devices is also limited. So all these limitations are an emerging challenges in front of scientists of this field ,they have to work more on toxic effects as well as drug loading problems and its targeted release increasing its

biocompatibility and making it more user as well as manufacture friendly . One major issue is their impact on natural environment is yet to be discussed properly in order to meet the specifications of regulatory bodies in the production of drugs coated with nanocarriers. Actually the cells which are to be treated with the help of this technology also have an effect on some properties of nanoparticles which acts as an limitation for nanoparticles. Nanoparticles of particular size sometime remain intact with the cells and can cause inflammatory responses inside the body which comes under the adverse side effect of drug coated with nanoparticles. Magnetic nanoparticles are trying to overcome all above mentioned problems gas they property of being attracted by magnetic fields. Specifically Inorganic magnetic nanoparticles which contain gadolinium as well as iron are proved to be more potent and enhanced agents as a drug delivery system. The inorganic magnetic nanoparticles are specifically proved as the contrast agent for MRI technique and it is approved by Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as discussed by Agnieszka Z and Wilczewska et.al., in 2012. So a lot is yet to be achieved in the field of nanomedicine in order to overcome all of its limitations as well as improving the targeted and diagnosis therapy for its use in future for various diseases and specially for treatment of cancer and for those diseases which are untreated till now.

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